

Schools and Digital Platform Use

Open Access Research Toolkit

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May 2025

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About this open-access research toolkit

This toolkit is one of the outputs of a research project that explored teachers, students and parents' experiences of digital platform use in the context of compulsory education. The project was funded by a BA/Leverhulme Small Research Grants SRG 2023 Round [SRG23\230440] and was conducted by [Anastasia Gouseti](#) and [Tricia Shaw](#). The aim of the toolkit is to bring research and practice closer together and to help other scholars and schools develop evidence-based understandings about the impact of school platformisation on teachers, students and parents by conducting further research in this area. This toolkit also aims to offer support with conducting methodologically sound and rigorous research that considers the various ethical implications that doing research with children and young people entails. Last, the research tools used for this project are made available for researchers and practitioners to adopt, adapt, and re-use, and step-by-step instructions for how to use these are provided.

How to use this toolkit

The toolkit is structured in thematic sections that align with the key methodological approaches and data collection practices that informed our research project. It can be used by educators, researchers, or policymakers interested in replicating this study with different participants and across various educational contexts. It is also useful for students wishing to gain a practical understanding of conducting qualitative research in education. You can work through sequentially for a comprehensive understanding of the adopted approach; dip into specific sections relevant to your immediate needs or interests; and download resources for carrying out fieldwork. While the toolkit is grounded in research, it has been designed to be flexible. You can use the various tools in their current form, or you can adapt templates, interview schedules, and the Blob Tree and diamond ranking activities to suit your institutional or cultural context.

As an open-access resource, the toolkit can be shared widely with colleagues and collaborators. We do encourage you to acknowledge the original authors by using this recommended citation: Gouseti, A. and Shaw, P.A. (2025) *Schools and Digital Platform Use: Open Access Research Toolkit*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15685720>

We are keen to receive feedback and hear about any project you carry out using this toolkit. If you'd like to connect with the research team, you email us at A.Gouseti@hull.ac.uk (Anastasia Gouseti) and Patricia.Shaw@hull.ac.uk (Tricia Shaw).

Methodology overview

This toolkit draws on a qualitative, participatory methodological approach to focus on listening closely to the experiences of teachers, students, and parents when it comes to digital platform use in schools. We used flexible, creative methods that allowed the participants to express their thoughts in different ways, not just through words, but also through images, sounds, and other non-verbal means (Cohen et al., 2017).

The research involved in-depth case studies of two secondary schools in England. We wanted to understand whether, and in what ways, digital platforms have become a primary 'space' for schools' operations since the Covid-19 pandemic. Moreover, this study was carried out in response to recent government policies that have encouraged schools in England to increase and 'optimise' their use of digital technologies (DfE, 2022). We specifically selected secondary schools because earlier research indicated that online home learning resources were used more widely in these schools during the pandemic, as a consequence of school closures (Andrew et al., 2020).

Our aim was to understand both the short- and long-term opportunities and challenges that come with the increasing use of digital platforms in schools. We wanted to explore how this shift, often called "platformisation", affects educators, students, and parents or carers. A key goal was also to build a shared understanding of what digital exclusion looks like and how we might address this.

To do this, we carried out individual interviews with Head teachers, senior school leaders, and Special Educational Needs Coordinators (SENCOs). We also held focus group discussions with teachers, students, and parents, using creative and participatory tools to help guide the conversations. You can find more details about these methods in the *Data Collection Tools* section.

We adopted purposive sampling, which is widely used in qualitative research for the identification and selection of information-rich cases related to the phenomenon of interest (Creswell & Clark, 2011), to attract two schools: a small coeducational school in rural East Yorkshire, and a small girls' school in London. The East Riding school is an active user of digital platforms, while the London school uses digital platforms in a targeted manner. Both schools were interested in exploring the impact of school platformisation.

We invited schools to take part in the research by sending an email and a short questionnaire. School leads were asked to answer a few questions about how digital platforms were used in their schools, read an information sheet about the project, and inform us if they were interested in being involved. To make sure we heard from a wide range of people, we invited teachers, parents or carers, and students from all year groups to take part. This helped us gather a variety of views and experiences.

In the spirit of inclusion, **all** students were invited to take part in the group activities, even if their parents or carers hadn't given formal consent. However, in these cases, we did **not** include any data from those students in our analysis. This approach allowed every student to feel involved without compromising ethical or legal standards.

We conducted a total of 2 Head teacher interviews, 2 senior leaders, 1 focus group and 18 individual interviews (total 21), 2 focus groups with parents and 6 individual interviews (total 10), and 5 focus groups with students and 8 individual interviews (total 36) across both schools.

In the student focus groups, we used a method called photo-elicitation — the idea of sharing images during a research conversation to help spark discussion (Harper, 2002; Bigante, 2010). This approach can help people express their thoughts more clearly by reacting to visual prompts (Thomas, 2009).

We chose images that represented different aspects of using digital platforms, including internet reliability, having a quiet space for homework, access to a device like a laptop or phone, the ability to print homework, support from adults, contacting teachers or classmates, staying motivated, attending homework clubs, and feeling monitored or supervised.

These images were then used in a diamond ranking activity. This is a thinking tool (Rockett & Percival, 2002) where participants work together to rank the images from most to least important. Through group discussion, reflection, and negotiation, they explain and share the reasons behind their choices (Clark, 2012). In our project, the activity encouraged the students to think deeply and collaboratively about their experiences with digital learning (see *Data Collection Tools* for more information).

In our analysis, we used a framework developed by Roland Barthes (1993) (usually applied to art and performance) to help us understand how the students chose and described images in the Blob Tree activity. This framework looks at how words and images relate to each other. Sometimes one is more important than the other (for example, when words explain a picture), and sometimes they're equally important and work together.

We focused on a type of relationship called "Anchorage," where the text helps guide the meaning of the image. We also used two of Barthes's concepts to dig deeper into the emotional responses the students had to the images. The first is the *punctum*, which is the part of an image that unexpectedly grabs your attention and creates a personal, emotional reaction. This concept was applied to the Blob Tree activity; by choosing specific characters, the students were able to express their emotions and talk about their experiences in a more personal way.

The second concept is the *studium*, which refers to the more general, shared understanding of an image. This was applied to analyse the transcripts from the photo-elicitation activity with students revealing their perspectives on key factors that influenced their use of digital

platforms, offering deeper insight into their experiences. Applying these concepts helped us explore how confident the students felt about using digital platforms.

Ethical considerations

This research project followed strict ethical standards set out by several organisations, including the British Academy and Leverhulme's ethics policy, the British Educational Research Association's (BERA) *Ethical Guidelines for Educational Research*, and the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) *Policy and Guidelines on Governance of Good Research Conduct*. We also followed the University of Hull's own procedures for working with teachers, parents/carers, and students in school settings.

Taking part in the research was completely voluntary. Everyone was given clear, age-appropriate information sheets that explained what the project was about, so they could decide for themselves whether or not they wanted to be involved. We asked adult participants to give formal permission to take part in the study. When it came to working with the students, we were very mindful of the ethical challenges involved. We understand that what's expected in theory doesn't always match what happens in real life when it comes to gaining consent.

We asked adult participants to formally opt in to the study by giving their consent. When working with the students, we were aware that ethical issues are more complex. As Cutting and Peacock (2021) point out, there's often a gap between the formal steps we're expected to follow and the realities of putting ethics into practice during research. To meet our legal responsibilities, we sent consent forms to parents and carers so their children could take part in the activities (see Appendix 1). At the same time, we followed guidance from Alderson and Morrow (2020) by also seeking the students' assent by asking them if they were happy to take part. We did this at the start of each focus group session.

During our data collection, we watched carefully for any signs, spoken or through body language, that a student might not want to continue. Although we didn't observe any signs of discomfort or refusal, students always had the option to leave the activity or withdraw from the research at any time. By using participatory and creative research methods, we attempted to reduce the power differences that can arise between adults and young people in research settings. This helped create a more comfortable and respectful space for students to express themselves.

To make sure participants were protected from any possible risk or harm, we took steps to keep their information confidential. This included anonymising the data so that no one could be identified from what they had shared. All data is stored securely and will be managed responsibly, including being disposed of in an ethical and appropriate way when the project ends.

This toolkit provides draft examples of consent forms for all participants that can be further adapted and used to facilitate research conducted in this field.

Data collection tools

Individual interviews

Individual interviews are a common and popular data collection tool in qualitative research. Interviews are mainly used to explore participants' experiences and perceptions in depth. They can range from highly structured interviews that use predetermined questions to more flexible, semi-structured or unstructured format that allow for open-ended discussions. The researcher usually records the interview through the use of audio recording devices when conducting an interview in person or, if the interview is conducted online, via the recording function of the videoconferencing tool used (e.g. Teams or Zoom). The recorded data is then transcribed for analysis or, in the case of online interviews, the generated transcript is downloaded and further edited for accuracy. Individual interviews are a valuable research tool in the field of social sciences as they can lead to the collection of rich and meaningful data.

For this project, individual semi-structured interviews were conducted either in person or online depending on the participant's preference. Consent forms were used and an interview schedule was developed (both shared in Appendices 1 and 2).

Practical tips:

- Before the interview develop an interview schedule but also be prepared to ask follow up questions during the discussion.
- Test your equipment to make sure it is working properly and bring spare batteries if needed.
- If the interview is online via a videoconferencing tool, ensure that you know how to use this to record a meeting. Perhaps try it out with a friend to avoid last minute technical issues.
- Consider having a second recording device for back-up.
- Choose a comfortable, neutral, accessible and quiet space if you are conducting the interview in person.
- Select a secure online platform that your institution subscribes to if the interview takes place online.
- Secure permission for audio or video recording via the consent form but also at the start of the discussion.
- If you are interviewing children or young people under the age of 16, you should gain consent from the parents and also gain the assent from the children and young people.
- Remind the participant about confidentiality and anonymity and their right to withdraw at any point during the interview.

- Be mindful of non-verbal cues or emotional reactions during the discussion.
- Thank the participant for their time and contribution.
- Write down any notes that were not captured by the audio recording immediately after the discussion.
- Transcribe the recordings as soon as possible after the discussion and delete any recordings that are no longer needed as per the information sheet you have provided.
- Store recordings and transcripts securely in line with ethical guidelines.

Focus Group interviews

Focus groups are widely used in qualitative research and are particularly valuable when the aim is to understand the perceptions, attitudes, and experiences of a group of participants. In this project focus groups were used with teachers, parents and students to gain insights into how they experienced digital platform use in the context of compulsory education. The focus groups with the teachers were guided by a semi-structured interview schedule while the focus groups with the parents and teachers also used participatory tools (blob trees and diamond ranking) to prompt discussions.

A focus group consists of a small group of participants (about 3-8 people) and the researcher who acts as a facilitator/moderator to encourage participation, keep the discussion on track and manage group dynamics. It is an efficient way to collect multiple perspectives, it can spark rich, interactive discussions and reveal consensus and disagreements. However, it may be challenging to manage dominant voices in the group and groups dynamics can influence what participants are willing to share. It also requires careful planning and while confidentiality is expected, it cannot be fully guaranteed in a group setting and the researcher needs to make participants aware of this.

For this project, semi-structured focus groups were conducted with teachers and parents either in person or online depending on the participants' preference. Consent forms were used, and an interview schedule was developed (both shared in Appendices 1 and 2).

Practical tips:

- Plan the logistics carefully to make the most of the focus group discussion. Aim for about 6 participants per session and try to have a mix of voices (male and female) as this will help with identifying participants during the transcription.
- Aim for a 50-60 minute session so that you have sufficient time to cover everything but avoid your participants getting tired. This is particularly relevant when doing research with younger children and a shorter session may be more appropriate for them.

- Choose a comfortable, neutral, accessible and quiet space if you are conducting the focus group in person.
- Select a secure online platform that your institution subscribes to if the focus group takes place online.
- Secure permission for audio or video recording via the consent form but also at the start of the discussion.
- If you are interviewing children or young people under the age of 16, you should gain consent from the parents and also gain the assent from the children and young people.
- Remind participants about confidentiality and anonymity and their right to withdraw at any point during the session.
- Be mindful of non-verbal cues or emotional reactions during the discussion.
- Thank the participants for their time and contribution.
- Write down any notes that were not captured by the audio recording immediately after the discussion.
- Transcribe the recordings as soon as possible after the discussion and delete any recordings that are no longer needed as per the information sheet you have provided.
- Store recordings and transcripts securely in line with ethical guidelines.

Blob Trees

Description

This participatory activity can be used with participants to explore how they feel about matters of importance to them. The Blobs are designed to be as simple as possible so that you can explore deep issues using feelings and body language. The Blobs are neither male nor female, young nor old, or from any specific period of time, country, or culture.

Objective

The aim of the activity in this research project was to encourage the participants to reflect on how they felt about using digital platforms. This approach focuses on understanding their reasoning behind selecting the Blob rather than interviewing the participants directly about their experiences.

Materials needed

- Printouts of the Blob Trees (see Appendix 3).
- Coloured pens or pencils.

Step by step instructions

Introduce the Activity:

- Explain the purpose of the activity.
- Provide participants with the printout of the Blob Tree.
- Allow time for participants to read and reflect on the content before starting to speak to them.
- Ask the participants to select which Blob(s) represent(s) how confident they feel about the area you are researching, and colour in the specific Blob.
- If the participants have both positive and negative feelings, ask them to use different colours to indicate this on the Blob Tree.

Figure 1: Example of Blob Tree activity from our project

Facilitate Discussion

- Encourage participants to explain their reasons for selecting the Blob(s).
- Ensure the focus is on understanding why the participant has selected the specific Blob(s) when asking questions rather than interviewing the participant.
- Ask each participant in turn about their Blob Tree.

Focus Group Discussion

- Facilitate a group discussion using questions such as:
 - I can see you have coloured in Blob 21. Can you tell me how you think it feels about...?
 - Why do you think the Blob might feel like that?
 - Can you think what might make the Blob feel happier/more confident/less stressed?
 - Has anyone else coloured in the same Blob?
 - Does anyone else feel the same way?

Please also see 'practical tips' provided in the 'Focus Groups' section.

Diamond Ranking

Description

This participatory activity can be used with participants to explore factors that impact them most within the area you are researching. They are asked to rank 9 images, that can be seen as facilitators or barriers, from most to least important.

Objective

The aim of the activity in this research project was to collaboratively rank 9 images relating to digital platform use, using a diamond-shaped layout (Rockett and Percival, 2002). This encouraged discussion and consensus-building among participants.

Materials needed

- Printouts of 9 images relating to digital platform use. This can be adapted to your area of research (see Appendix 4).

- A large surface such as a table or the floor to lay these on.

Step by step instructions

Introduce the Activity:

- Explain the purpose of the activity.
- Ensure participants understand that there is no single 'correct' ranking—discussion and reasoning are key.
- Provide participants with the images.
- Allow time for participants to look at, reflect on the images, and begin arranging the images before asking any questions.

Create an Initial Ranking:

Ask participants to work as a group to arrange the images in a diamond shape:

- 1 image at the top (most important)
- 2 images in the second row
- 3 images in the third row
- 2 images in the fourth row
- 1 image at the bottom (least important)

Figure 2: Example of diamond ranking activity from our project

Facilitate discussion and adjustments

- Encourage participants to discuss and justify their reasoning for the layout of the images.
- Remember to ask questions about the position of the image rather than questioning the participant directly – Why would having your own space be more important than internet connectivity or reliability?
- Allow participants to move the images and change the ranking ensuring everyone has a say before finalising the ranking based on consensus.
- If disagreements arise, ask participants to explain their perspectives and try to find common ground. If this is not possible, don't worry as the purpose of the activity is to understand the participants' different perspectives.

Record the final ranking

- Once the participants agree on the final ranking, document the result by taking a photo (if you have multiple groups remember to make a note of which ranking belongs to which group).

Focus group discussion

- Facilitate a short discussion on the following themes:
 - What was easy or difficult about reaching a consensus?
 - Were there any surprising rankings?
 - How does this ranking inform future decisions or actions?
- Summarise the key takeaways and thank participants for their contributions.

Please also see 'practical tips' provided in the 'Focus Groups' section.

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Appendix 1: Information sheet and consent forms

These are available as Word documents through the links below. You should edit the forms according to the context of your own project:

[Information sheet and consent form for Head teachers](#)

[Information sheet and consent form for teachers](#)

[Information sheet and consent form for parents](#)

[Participant information sheet to be shared with students before the beginning of the interview activity](#)

Appendix 2: Interview and focus group sample questions

Also available as a printable Word document [here](#)

Questions for headteachers/teachers/other school staff

- What digital platforms do you use at your school?
- Who is responsible for selecting these?
- Is it possible to opt out?
- Was platform use accelerated during the pandemic?
- What do you use these digital platforms for?
- Have you reviewed the use of these platforms? (e.g. have you collected feedback from students and parents?)
- What are the opportunities that you identify relating to the use of these digital platforms? (prompts: streamlining processes, increasing efficiency, supporting administration, facilitating communication with students/parents)
- What are the issues/challenges you have faced? (prompts: data protection, digital inequalities, surveillance, performativity, workload)
- How empowered (or disempowered) does digital platform use make you feel?
- How has digital platform use reshaped organisational, teaching or other practices at your school? (e.g. changes of processes, priorities etc.)
- How do staff and students (or parents) acquire the digital skills required to use these platforms effectively and safely?
- How do you see the future in relation to the use of digital platforms at your school?
- Is there anything else you would like to add that I might not have asked you?

Questions for parents

- What digital platforms does your child's school use? (give examples if needed)
- What are these platforms used for?
- What are the opportunities that you identify relating to the use of these digital platforms? (prompts: ease of communication, teaching and learning opportunities etc.)
- What are the issues/challenges you have faced? (prompts: digital skills, language barriers, digital access, increased parental responsibility to monitor your child)
- How empowered (or disempowered) does digital platform use make you feel?

- What would you like to see more of in relation to digital platform use at your child's school?
- What would you like to see less of in relation to digital platform use at your child's school?
- What suggestions would you make for the future?
- Is there anything else you would like to add that I might not have asked you?

Appendix 3: Printout for the Blob Tree activity

Also available as a printable Word document [here](#)

Appendix 4: Images for the Diamond Ranking activity

You will need to print these and cut them out so that the students can then arrange the images in a diamond shape.

Please note these are the ones used for this particular project, and they are indicative of some themes we have identified as relevant. They are intended to assist others doing research around digital platform use in schools, but you can adapt the images to what you think may be more relevant within your chosen context.

Internet connectivity/ reliability [Photo by [Paul Hanaoka](#) on [Unsplash](#)]

Contact the teachers/ classmates [Photo by [Brett Jordan](#) on [Unsplash](#)]

Printing [Photo by [Joonas Sild](#) on [Unsplash](#)]

Own or communal space for doing homework [Photo by [Tran Mau Tri Tam](#) on [Unsplash](#)]

Own laptop/computer/phone [Photo by [Thomas Park](#) on [Unsplash](#)]

Parent/adult support [Photo by [sofatutor](#) on [Unsplash](#)]

Motivation [Photo by [Brett Jordan](#) on [Unsplash](#)]

School homework clubs [Photo by [Haseeb Modi](#) on [Unsplash](#)]

Surveillance [Photo by [Tobias Tullius](#) on [Unsplash](#)]

Acknowledgement

This open-access research toolkit is an output of the research project 'The platformised school: widening opportunities or exacerbating inequalities?' funded by BA/Leverhulme Small Research Grants [SRG23\230440]

Citation

Please cite as: Gouseti, A. and Shaw, P.A. (2025) *Schools and Digital Platform Use: Open Access Research Toolkit*. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15685720>